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IMPROVING THE RELIABILITY AND EFFICIENCY OF POWER SUPPLY IN OIL EXTRACTION FACILITIES

Abstract:

The main load demanding devices used in oil production facilities are asynchronous and synchronous motors. Due to the fact that these devices require a large amount of starting current, and because they are reactive power-demanding structures, their efficient operation as consumers of electricity will directly affect the efficiency and reliability of the internal and external power supply network. From this point of view, increasing the reliability and efficiency of electricity supply in oil extraction facilities is a priority issue.

Keywords: Asynchronous motor, voltage gap, quality indicator, switching process, inverter, rectifier, deep inputs.

1. Introduction

The study of the typical characteristics of the equipment used in oil extraction facilities and the changes in electrical parameters under different operating modes can provide insights into the discussed issues. One of the key aspects to consider is that high-power electric motors will always have high starting currents under any circumstances [1]. On the other hand, since these motors are inductive loads, they are likely to generate high harmonics due to the influence of their electromagnetic fields and have a significantly high reactive power demand [1].

The dependence of electrical and electromechanical parameters on time during the startup of asynchronous motors in oil extraction facilities is shown in Figure 1.1. From this graph, it is evident that the starting

current is initially much higher and stabilizes as the rotor reaches its nominal speed. However, the critical point to focus on is that the power demand of the motor fluctuates sharply in an unstable manner from the moment it is switched on. This is related to the electromechanical transition process and is physically observed as oscillations and vibrations [2].

If this issue is not mitigated or eliminated, it will lead to the rapid wear and tear of the mechanical parts connected to the motor and cause the emergence of harmonics in the power supply network, which are difficult to suppress. Since the source of these harmonics is mechanical parts with high inertia, their elimination is quite challenging.

Figure 1.1. Graph of rotor frequency, power, and current dependence on time during the startup of an asynchronous motor

Another issue is the presence of a 6kV or 10kV power supply system in these areas. The existence of such networks leads to several problems and inefficiencies [3]. In most existing supply schemes, a 35kV voltage is first stepped down to 6kV or 10kV through the main step-down substation. Then, the 6kV or 10kV lines are fed into 10/0.4kV or 6/0.4kV transformer stations, where multiple asynchronous motor groups are connected [3].

This means that the supply system consists of three voltage levels, requiring two consecutive transformers. Considering the operating costs, failures, and losses associated with each transformer, it is necessary to review these types of supply schemes.

2. Proposals

As mentioned earlier, to avoid the high inrush currents of asynchronous motors, instead of directly supplying network frequency to the stator windings, the

frequency of the current should be gradually increased from zero Hz to nominal frequency. This process is performed using an inverter device. However, for the inverter to function, the alternating current from the network must first be converted into direct current and then supplied to IGBT transistors to obtain the desired frequency of alternating current [4].

The complete device that performs this process is called a **VFD (Variable Frequency Drive)**, and its general working principle is illustrated in Figure 1.2. Another advantage of this device is that it allows the motor to be controlled at any desired speed, ensuring optimal operation.

Figure 1.2. Frequency-controlled mechanism for starting an asynchronous motor

Another proposed mechanism is the direct deep-entry power supply method. The existing power supply scheme in oil extraction facilities is illustrated in Figure

1.3. In this method, instead of using a 10/0.4kV transformer station after a 35/10kV transformer, a **direct 35/0.4kV transformer** is used. The proposed new scheme is presented in Figure 1.4.

Figure 1.3. Existing supply scheme used in oil extraction facilities.

Figure 1.4. Deep-entry 35/0.4kV power supply scheme.

3. Conclusion

The implementation of both methods helps eliminate specific inefficiencies. The first approach prevents the excessive loading of the power supply network due to high starting currents. This ensures the longevity and

quality of electrical equipment operation while improving the reliability of contact connections by eliminating instantaneous current surges. The reduction of maximum inrush currents also prevents **voltage sag** during power restoration.

In the second case, reducing the number of power transformers decreases the number of failure sources, making operation more efficient. Increasing the voltage level results in a reduction of current in the supply lines, which in turn minimizes power losses. Considering that technical losses depend on the square of the transmission voltage, increasing the voltage by **3.5 times leads to an approximately 12-fold reduction in losses.**

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